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The Effect of Power Point presentations on Retention of B.Ed. Teacher Trainees

Dr. Pratibha Sagar*, and Prof. Dr. N. N. Pandey**

Abstract

In the present study the effect of PowerPoint presentations on retention of B.Ed. teacher trainees has been examined. The study used two intact classes (62 students in each) of B.Ed. Specialization students. An achievement test developed and standardized by researcher was administered on both classes to obtain pre-test scores. Both classes were taught the same content for 34 instructional days (40 minutes per day). In experimental class students were taught by lecture supported by PowerPoint presentations to learn the content while control group was taught by traditional lecture. After experimentation post-test scores on achievement test were obtained. Then the same test was administered after a gap of 15 day for retention. Data analyzed through analysis of covariance revealed that there is significant difference between the two teaching methods with regard to retention of the content of the teacher trainees and retention of girls was better than boys using Power Point.

The use of technology is becoming increasingly popular as a teaching and learning tool in education. Some instructors have enthusiastically adopted technological innovations in their classrooms (Craig and Amernic, 2006), while others have resisted the trend (Stewart, 2001). So, the debate on the importance of using computer technology in developing the

educational process remains as uncertain as it is unsettling whether the technology enhances learning or not (Watson et al., 2007). As such technology provides several advantages on traditional education and has the potential to enhance teaching and learning (Amare, 2006). One form of this technology is Microsoft PowerPoint software which has become an accepted lecture aid in higher education and is frequently used to visually present the main points of classroom lectures. In the classroom setting, PowerPoint can help ensure that the main points of a lecture are clearly made. According to Yaworski (2001), PowerPoint helps speakers organize their thoughts and present them in a clear and concise manner while using multi-sensory tactics to hold audience attention. As a result of these and other advantages, PowerPoint presentations have become a popular way of presenting information to audiences of all kinds, and are rapidly becoming the standard for academic presentations. "PowerPoint should be recognized as a new communication medium that is fundamentally changing the nature and dynamic of how we teach" (Craig & Amernic, 2006).

Humans receive data through multiple channels, i.e. media, including audio and visual channels (Paivio, 1969) as well as touch, taste and smell. Multimedia is most commonly defined as the use of at least two of these elements:

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sound (audio), and text, still graphics, and motion graphics (visual) (Tannenbaum, 1998). The importance of multi-channel communication confirms that when information is presented by more than one channel, there will be additional reinforcement, resulting in greater retention and improved learning (Ellis, 2004; Bagui, 1998; Daniels, 1999). PowerPoint presentations incorporate graphics, animation, and colour (imagery). It possesses multiple attributes designed to produce more sensory stimulation. In relation to the visual sense, such PowerPoint presentations allow instructors to move from static to dynamic visuals; slides can incorporate motion through features such as transition effects, builds, and animation. These slides allow instructors to enhance lectures with both auditory and visual stimuli. Reynolds and Baker (1987) find that presenting materials on a computer increased attention and learning, and learning increased as attention increased.

The graphical nature of the PowerPoint presentation arouses students' imagery systems, which become more activated when information is presented in non-verbal forms. PowerPoint presentations could contribute to comprehension, and improve short and long-term memory. Since, in a PowerPoint presentation, topics are presented in a hierarchical fashion with graphics, colour, and animation, students could "use a mental image of that outline to study, to retrieve the information on a test" (Clark and Paivio, 1991, p. 176). Rose (2001) also notes that presentation of learning materials in graphical form is beneficial for students.

It goes without saying that good teaching is not simply presenting content to students, but

must foster students' connections to content and promote student retention of facts and concepts (Mason & Hlynka, 1998). Also critical is the effect of any teaching aid on verbal interaction between students and the instructor, or students with other students. In fact, verbal interaction is considered highly desirable by most instructors, and discussion is generally believed to enhance understanding and retention (Diaz-Rico & Weed, 1995; Kryspin & Feldhusen, 1974; Richards & Rodgers, 1986). Maddux et al. (2001) agree and argue that students learn best when they are actively constructing new knowledge. So the instructors must design and present information in a way that allows students the ability to process information (Apperson et al., 2008; Sweller & Chandler, 1994). If presentations leave relationships and associations between ideas and concepts unspecified, 'generic, superficial, simplistic thinking' will result (Tufté, 2003).

However, there has been no research on whether PowerPoint improves student retention of facts and concepts presented in a lecture or not. Also there is dearth of studies whether PowerPoint stimulates, depresses, or has no effect on classroom verbal interaction. The purpose of the present study is to investigate whether there is a difference in retention of B.Ed. teacher trainees taught by PowerPoint presentations and traditional lecture formats with identical content.

Several studies point to the idea that graphics improve students recall (ChanLin, 1998, 2000; Lowry, 1999, Atkins-Sayre, 1998). Structured presentations may affect students' learning from the lectures as the organizational structure of instructional material is related to

students' understanding (Miller and McCown, 1986) and their retention of the material (Garner, 1992). Some felt that the visual emphasis in PowerPoint helped them recall the lecture material at the time of examination.

Studies by Atkin-Sayre et al. (1998), ChanLin (1998, 2000), Lowry (1999), Hlynka and Mason (1998), Miller and McCown (1986), Garner (1992), Pittman (1985), Pascarella et al. (1996) show that students who were taught with the aid of presentation graphics believed that they were better able to learn or retain the material from class.

Majority of studies favour the better retention by PowerPoint presentations, however a study by Savoy et al. (2009) about information retention in students, the majority of students expressed a preference for passive learning through PowerPoint, students retained 15% less information than those in lectures where information was delivered by more traditional means. Moreover the researchers could not trace out any study related to this in Indian context. Hence a need was felt to study the effect of PowerPoint presentation on retention of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

Objectives of the Study

In view of the above-mentioned considerations, the present investigation has the following objectives:

1. To study the effect of PowerPoint presentation on retention of content of B.Ed. teacher trainees.
2. To explore gender differences in retention of content of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

3. To find out the effect of interaction between gender and teaching method on retention of content of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

Hypotheses

Keeping in view the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses are formulated in null form:

- H01: There is no significance difference in the mean retention of B.Ed. teacher trainees taught by lecture method and lecture accompanied by PowerPoint presentation.
- H02: Boys and girls B.Ed. teacher trainees do not differ significantly in relation to their retention of content.
- H03: Teaching method by gender of B.Ed. teacher trainees will not significantly affect retention.

Methodology

This research is experimental in nature where pre-test -post-test, non equivalent control group design was used. Three B.Ed. specialization courses run in MJP Rohilkhand University, Bareilly campus, out of which teacher trainees of B.Ed. (Specialization in Vocational Education) and B.Ed. (Specialization in Educational Computing) groups were chosen. Two groups B.Ed. (Educational Computing), the experimental group, taught through PowerPoint presentations and B.Ed. Vocational Education, the control group, taught through traditional lecture method, were selected for the study. One intact class served as the experimental group and the other as the control group. Treatments were assigned randomly.

Achievement Test - (AT), developed and validated by the researchers, was used for the investigation. Since the study aimed at finding out the relative effect of two different methods of teaching, the test was designed to assess the degree to which learners acquired the content taught to them. Two chapters from Educational Psychology, namely learning and learning theories were selected for teaching in the study and the achievement test was based on these two chapters.

Teacher competence was controlled as the researcher himself taught both the experimental and control groups. Length of instruction was also controlled as each teaching session in each group lasted for one period of 40 minutes. Teaching session was planned for morning and afternoon time for control group and experimental group respectively on one day and next day morning time was allotted to experimental group and afternoon time for control group. Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to analyse data where post-test achievement scores was taken as covariate.

The total experimentation procedure was

planned and organized in successive steps in order to facilitate proper collection of data. Firstly achievement test was administered for pre-test scores then both the groups were taught for 34 working days. After a gap of two days, achievement test was again administered for post-test scores. Then again after 14 days, same test was administered for retention scores.

Analysis and Discussion

After data collection and scoring of tests, the data was analyzed using relevant statistical techniques. In addition to the general descriptive statistics, t-test and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) were used to analyze the data.

In order to find out the effect of PowerPoint presentations on retention, effect of gender on retention and interaction of method of teaching and gender, 2×2 ANCOVA was carried out on post - post achievement test, taking post test scores as covariate. Means and standard deviation have been presented in Table 1.1 and the results of ANCOVA for retention have been shown in Table 1.2.

Table 1.1 Retention - Mean and standard deviation

		N	Mean	Standard Deviation
	Control Boys	49	42.82	12.65
	Control Girls	13	45.92	8.48
Retention	Total	62	43.67	11.41
	Exp. Boys	40	49.45	12.64
	Exp. Girls	22	67.05	13.69
	Total	62	55.69	15.18

Table 1.2 Summary of ANCOVA for Retention

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F
Group (Teaching method)	1367.390	1	1367.390	19.940**
Gender	415.490	1	415.490	6.059*
Teaching Method * Gender	603.182	1	603.182	8.796**
Error	8160.539	119	68.576	
Total	331626	124		

** - Significant at 0.01 level of significance, * - Significant at 0.05 level

A perusal of the above table confirms that the F value for the main effect of group on retention was significant ($F=19.940, p<0.01$). The significant F tells that the experimental and control groups differed in retention. Hence, the hypothesis that "there is no significance difference in the mean retention of B.Ed. teacher trainees taught by lecture method and lecture accompanied by PowerPoint presentation" is rejected. Further, the F value for the main effect of gender on retention was also significant ($F=6.059, p<0.05$). It means that boys and girls differed significantly in retention. Therefore, the hypothesis that "boys and girls

B.Ed. teacher trainees do not differ significantly in relation to their retention of content" was also rejected. The F value for the interaction effect of group and gender on retention was also found to be significant ($F=8.796, p<0.01$) meaning thereby that boys and girls differ in retention under the two teaching methods, the traditional method and PowerPoint presentation. Thus, the hypothesis that "teaching method by gender of B.Ed. teacher trainees will not significantly affect retention" was also rejected.

To further probe into the matter, adjusted means for retention were calculated. These means have been shown in Table 1.3.

Table 1.3 Adjusted means - Retention

Retention	Control	Experimental	Total
Boys	46.561	49.406	47.983
Girls	45.859	58.824	52.342
Total	46.210	54.115	50.162

An enquiry of means for the two groups on the retention (Table 1.3) infers that the experimental group (mean = 54.115)

outperformed the control group (mean = 46.210) with respect to retention. Looking at the adjusted means for boys and girls on the retention

discloses that girls' (mean=52.342) retention was better than the boys (mean=47.983). To further explain the effect of interaction, a graph was

plotted between the adjusted means for different groups on retention (Table 1.3), and the same has been presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 Adjusted Means for Retention

A perusal of the above graph shows that the two lines joining control and experimental means are not parallel. If the lines are extended, they will intersect each other. This tells that the interaction between gender and teaching method for retention was significant. The significant interaction between gender and method implies

that boys' and girls' have different retention of content under the two teaching methods, the traditional method and PowerPoint.

To find out which groups differ significantly, t - value was calculated. The t-values are shown in Table 1.4

Table 1.4 t-values

Groups		t - Value
Control Boys	Control Girls	0.24 NS
Control Boys	Experimental Girls	3.74 **
Control Boys	Experimental Boys	1.08 NS
Experimental Boys	Experimental Girls	2.74 **
Experimental Boys	Control Girls	1.15 NS
Experimental Girls	Control Girls	3.55 **

The t - value, as shown in Table 1.4, revealed there is no significant difference between control boys and control girls, control boys and experimental boys and experimental boys and control girls, whereas high significant differences were found between control boys and experimental girls, experimental boys and experimental girls and experimental girls and control girls.

Hence it may be said that PowerPoint facilitates acquisition of retention better than the traditional method. The reasons for superiority of PowerPoint over traditional method with regard to retention may be numerous. These may include use of more than one sense, structuring of presentation as organized material may facilitate student's understanding and recall and visual emphasis in presentation and fostering students' connections to content (Mason & Hlynka, 1998). The finding that PowerPoint presentation produces significantly more retention than the traditional method is in tune with the results obtained earlier by (Harknett and Cobane, 1997, Haugland, 1997, Atkins-Sayre et al., 1998, ChanLin, 1998, 2000; Lowry, 1999, Tufte, 2003, Nouri and Shahid, 2005, Craig and Amernic, 2006, Lever-Duffy et al., 2003, Parkindon and Hollamby, 2003, Fernald 1988, Mayer & Anderson, 1992, Mercer & Mercer, 2001, Mousavi et al., 1995, Murphy, 1997 and Shelly et al., 2004). Structured presentations may affect students' learning from the lectures as the organizational structure of instructional material is related to students' understanding (Miller and McCown, 1986) and their retention of the material (Garner, 1992).

The reasons for superiority of girls in retention over boys may be numerous including sincerity of girls, as it is seen nowadays that in every exam girls outperform boys, more focussed than boys, awareness of education, carrier orientation and holding a good position in family and society. Although no study could be located to support or refute this finding, it may be concluded that retention is better for girls as compared to boys. This may be due to difference in socio-cultural background of the sample subjects. The reasons for superiority of girls in retention may include sincerity of girls as it is seen nowadays that in every exam girls outperformed boys, awareness for education, carrier orientation and holding a good position in family and society and parental support, as discussed earlier. Whatever be the reasons, it was concluded that girls outperform boys in retention under PowerPoint presentation method.

IMPLICATIONS

Lectures involving PowerPoint presentations resulted in better student retention of the material than traditional lectures with no presentation aids. Mean student test scores were higher as compared to traditional lectures. It might be that the way in which PowerPoint slides change as each point is brought up holds students' attention more effectively than simply uncovering points. Bringing up major points one by one on PowerPoint slides might have helped students focus better on one concept at a time. Moreover, when visual presentation aid is used in lectures, the content may be more articulated, clarified, and enhanced visually. This idea is consistent

with the theory that a multisensory approach produces learning that is superior to an approach that makes use of a single sensory modality. When information is presented with presentation aids, students hear the words, see the words, and often take notes, making the sensory input visual, auditory and tactile.

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